

**NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS OF CROSS-FLOW EFFECTS ON SEPARATED-
TRANSITION FLOW IN LOW-REYNOLDS-NUMBER COMPRESSOR CASCADE**

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ABSTRACT

At low Reynolds numbers (Re), intense secondary flows exist in the compressor cascade corner region, which significantly disturb the flow characteristics of the suction-side separated shear layer and impact aerodynamic performance and flow stability. This study conducts Large Eddy Simulation (LES) on the flow within a subsonic compressor cascade under low Re conditions ($Re=2.5 \times 10^5$), combined with the multiscale Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (mPOD) method, to systematically investigate the crossflow effects on the transition mechanisms of the suction-side separated shear layer. The results indicate that the crossflow substantially disrupts the spanwise coherence of the separated bubble, leading to the sequential appearance of short, medium, long, and secondary separation bubbles from the blade root to the midspan. Their evolution is directly governed by the path and intensity of the crossflow. In the near-endwall region ($z/H < 0.14$), the crossflow-induced vortex (CFIV) becomes the dominant structure. This vortex, generated by the

interaction between the crossflow jet and the separated shear layer, promotes the downstream propagation of three-dimensional oblique waves, significantly altering the transition process. Modal analysis of the turbulent kinetic energy production term (P_{TKE}) reveals that the CFIV dominates P_{TKE} at $z/H < 0.14$, whereas the K-H spanwise vortices play a primary role at $z/H > 0.14$. The transition boundary between the dominant mechanisms coincides with the location where the crossflow fully enters the separation bubble. This study proposes a new model of "crossflow-induced transition", elucidating the spatial competition mechanism between crossflow and K-H instability. It not only provides a novel explanation for the transition mechanism in the cascade corner region but also offers new insights for controlling compressor profile losses at low Re , indicating that suppressing crossflow development is as crucial as managing boundary layer separation.

Keywords: unsteady aerodynamics, low Reynolds number, crossflow, separated shear layer, transition

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NOMENCLATURE

C	chord
C_{ax}	axial chord
d	normal distance
f	frequency
Ma	Mach number
P_{TKE}	turbulent kinetic energy production
Re	Reynolds number
St	Strouhal number
τ	pitch
TKE	turbulent kinetic energy
u	transient velocity
u'	fluctuation velocity
U	average velocity
ν	kinematic viscosity
χ	Kolmogorov scale
γ	intermittency factor
δ^*	displacement thickness
θ	momentum thickness
CFL	Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy
CFIV	crossflow-induced vortex
K-H	Kelvin–Helmholtz
LES	large-eddy simulations
mPOD	multiscale Proper Orthogonal Decomposition
PV	passage vortex
PSD	Power Spectrum Density
SV	spanwise vortex
T-S	Tollmien–Schlichting

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern high-altitude long-endurance unmanned aerial vehicles require aero-engine compressors to achieve higher stage loading within a more compact design [1]. At the resulting low Reynolds number (Re), compressor flows exhibit complex separation behaviors that are difficult to accurately predict numerically [2], especially the extent of the separation bubble's plateau region—a phenomenon closely tied to laminar separation and the subsequent transition process. Understanding the mechanisms of separation-induced transition and reattachment is therefore essential for reliable engineering design and performance prediction.

Current understanding of separation-induced transition in rotating machinery is largely based on studies of two-dimensional cascades, where inviscid Tollmien–Schlichting (T–S) and viscous Kelvin–Helmholtz (K–H) instabilities have been recognized as the primary drivers of boundary layer transition [3]. In actual compressor environments, however, secondary flows introduce cross-flow instability, altering transition behavior along the span [4]. This shift in dominant instability mechanisms under three-dimensional pressure fields has been noted in separated flows by Yaras [5]. Similarly, Toppings et al. [6] observed on airfoils that tip-vortex-induced spanwise cross-flow can suppress boundary layer separation near the tip while reducing T–S instability intensity.

In flows with coupled crossflow and separated shear layer instability, the transition typically manifests as a hybrid

transition mechanism, complicating the prediction and detection of three-dimensional boundary layer transition locations [4,7,8]. Current understanding of the coupling mechanisms between crossflow and separated-transition flow in compressors remains incomplete.

Thus, this study conducts large-eddy simulations (LES) on a high-subsonic compressor cascade V103, designed to systematically investigate the separated-transition characteristics of boundary layers at different spanwise locations under low- Re condition, with a focus on elucidating the coupled interactions between crossflow and K–H instability. The numerical and experimental methods are described first. Then the separation bubble structures at different spanwise positions is compared. Third, the mechanism of crossflow-induced transition in the separated shear layer is elucidated. Finally, the spatial competition mechanism between the crossflow and the K–H instability is clarified. The results provide a novel explanation for the transition mechanism in the cascade corner region and will assist in profile losses control and performance improvement under low Re conditions.

2. NUMERICAL SETUP

2.1 Reference cascade geometry

A high subsonic axial compressor cascade V103, designed based on NACA 65 K48 [9], is used in this study, as shown in Figure. 1. The geometric and aerodynamic parameters of the cascade are listed in Table 1.

FIGURE 1: V103 CASCADE

Design parameter	Symbol	Magnitude
Chord, mm	C	40
Axial chord, mm	C_{ax}	36.9
Height, mm	H	40
Pitch, mm	τ	22
Inlet flow angle, °	β_1	132
Outlet flow angle, °	β_2	96
Stagger angle, °	β_s	112.5
Inlet Mach number	Ma	0.67

TABLE 1: GEOMETRY AND AERODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF V103 CASCADE

2.2 Numerical strategy

The high-fidelity numerical simulations are conducted using the open-source finite-volume compressible Navier-Stokes solver rhoPimpleFoam based on OpenFOAM (Open-source Field Operation And Manipulation). To generate inflow turbulence at the inlet, the divergence-free synthetic eddy method (DFSEM) [10] is implemented by prescribing Reynolds stresses, turbulence integral length scales, and velocity vectors. Furthermore, the wall-adapted local eddy-viscosity SGS model (LES WALE model [11]) is employed to calculate the subgrid-scale viscosity. The advantage of the WALE model is that it is highly adaptive for wall-bounded flows and can reproduce the laminar-to-turbulent transition in conjunction with automatically returning the correct wall-asymptotic variation of SGS viscosity:

$$\mu_{sgs} = (C_w \Delta)^2 \frac{(S_{ij}^d S_{ij}^d)^{3/2}}{(S_{ij}^d S_{ij}^d)^{5/2} + (S_{ij}^d S_{ij}^d)^{5/4}} \quad (1)$$

where $\overline{S_{ij}}$ is the strain rate tensor, and S_{ij}^d is as followed:

$$S_{ij}^d = \frac{1}{2} (\overline{g_{ij}^2} + \overline{g_{ji}^2}) - \frac{1}{3} \overline{\delta_{ij} g_{kk}^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\overline{g_{ij}^2} = \frac{\partial \overline{u_i}}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial \overline{u_k}}{\partial x_j} \quad (3)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker symbol, and $C_w = 0.5$ is calibrated for decaying isotropic turbulence.

2.3 Boundary conditions and computational mesh

Figure. 2 illustrates the computational domain along with the applied boundary conditions. The spanwise height is set to $0.5H$ ($H = C = 40$ mm); this aspect ratio ensures a two-dimensional flow pattern near the upper boundary (shroud). The lower boundary (hub) is defined as a no-slip adiabatic wall, while the shroud is treated as a symmetry wall. Pitchwise periodicity is enforced. Inlet and outlet boundaries are positioned $1.5C_{ax}$ upstream of the leading edge and $2.5C_{ax}$ downstream of the trailing edge, respectively.

FIGURE 2: COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

A low Re condition of $Re = 2.5 \times 10^5$ is selected [12]. At the inlet, velocity (u, v, w) and total temperature (T_{tl}) are prescribed, while static pressure (P_2) is imposed at the outlet. By adjusting u, v, w, T_{tl} , and P_2 , the inlet Re can be adjusted at 2.5×10^5 , with the inlet Ma held constant at 0.67. The dynamic viscosity of air is calculated using Sutherland's law:

$$\frac{\mu}{\mu_{ref}} = \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \frac{T_{ref} + S}{T + S} \quad (4)$$

In Equation (4), S denotes the Sutherland temperature (110.4 K). The reference temperature T_{ref} and dynamic viscosity μ_{ref} are 273.15 K and 1.716×10^{-5} kg/(m·s), respectively. And inlet turbulence intensity is 1%.

The computational grid, constructed with an O4H topology, is shown in Figure. 3. A single blade passage contains approximately 5×10^7 grid nodes. As indicated in Figure. 4(a), the maximum wall units in the axial, pitchwise, and spanwise directions are constrained to values below 15, 0.4, and 8, respectively, meeting the mesh resolution criteria for LES [13]. Furthermore, the Kolmogorov scales (χ) is calculated:

$$\chi = (\rho \nu^3 / \varepsilon)^{1/4} \quad (5)$$

Here, ν is the kinematic viscosity and ε represents the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) dissipation rate. Under the assumption of local equilibrium, ε is approximated by the TKE production term. Distributions of the the mesh resolution in Kolmogorov scales at $x/C_{ax} = 0.8$ and 1.2, presented in Figure. 4 (b), show a maximum value below 25, consistent with the ranges reported by You [14] and Cui [15].

FIGURE 3: COMPUTATIONAL GRID

FIGURE 4: MESH QUALITY: (a) NORMALIZED GRID SIZE AND (b) MESH RESOLUTION IN KOLMOGOROV SCALES (χ)

A time step of 2×10^{-7} s is adopted to maintain a Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) number around 0.7. Each physical time step includes ten inner iterations, reducing the maximum residual below 10^{-4} . Convergence monitoring indicated that roughly 45,000 time steps (equivalent to 46 through-flow times) are needed to reach a statistically steady state. Subsequently, data for statistical analysis were gathered over an additional 10,000 time steps (10 through-flow times).

2.4 Numerical validation of LES

To verify the reliability of the numerical method, the predicted isentropic Ma (Ma_{isen} is defined as Equation (6)) at the two spanwise positions is compared with test data [16]. As shown in Figure. 5, the LES results show good agreement with experimental data in the Ma_{isen} distribution across both spanwise positions. The simulation accurately captured key flow features, including the separation and transition points—identified by the start and end of the plateau region, demonstrating that the numerical method used in this study is convincing in predicting the transition process in the compressor cascade.

$$Ma_{isen} = \sqrt{\left(\left(\frac{P_{t1}}{P} \right)^{\frac{k-1}{k}} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{2}{k-1}} \quad (6)$$

FIGURE 5: EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL RESULTS OF THE Ma_{isen} DISTRIBUTION FOR V103 CASCADE AT DIFFERENT SPANWISE POSITIONS OF (a) $z/H=0.15$ AND (b) $z/H=0.5$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Spanwise incoherence of separation bubbles under the influence of end-wall effects

Under the influence of the end-wall boundary layer, low-energy fluid is driven by the blade loading from the pressure side to the suction side. When this low-energy fluid rolls up onto the suction side, it significantly alters the flow near the suction-side corner region. This section investigates the impact of end-wall effects on the structure of the suction-side separation bubble.

As observed in Figure. 6 from the limiting streamlines and $U_x=0$ iso-surface, flow separation occurs on the suction surface. The reattachment and transition positions, as well as the thickness of the separation bubble, exhibit substantial incoherence across the entire spanwise direction. A mean transition location is defined by the streamwise location of maximum shape factor ($H_x = \delta_x^*/\theta_x$) [17]. This incoherence is particularly pronounced in the corner region. Along the span from the end-wall to the mid-span, the separation bubble manifests four distinct patterns: (1) short separation bubble ($z/H < 0.1$), (2) medium separation bubble ($0.1 < z/H < 0.14$), (3) long separation bubble ($0.14 < z/H < 0.3$), and (4) secondary separation bubble ($z/H > 0.3$).

FIGURE 6: THE LIMITED STREAMLINES AT SUCTION SURFACE AND $U_x=0$ ISO-SURFACE

Analysis of the limiting streamlines indicates that these four patterns are closely associated with crossflow originating from

the end-wall. Crossflow-induced separation^[18] forms near the base of the separation bubble, with the separation line defining the boundary between the short and medium separation bubbles. The crossflow penetrates into main body of the medium separation bubble from its base, causing reversal of axial flow direction. This crossflow impinges on the rear part of the medium bubble, leading to concave indentation. Furthermore, beyond $z/H > 0.3$, the crossflow realigns with the main streamwise direction, causing separated shear layer to undergo reattachment followed by another separation in region (4).

The intensity of the crossflow varies along the spanwise direction during its development. As shown in Figure. 7(a), the width of the blue iso-surface increases gradually from the blade root until $z/H = 0.1$, after which it gradually narrows. Meanwhile, the spanwise velocity reaches its peak near $z/H = 0.1$ (see Figure. 7(b)), indicating that the width of the crossflow is directly related to the $U_{z,max}$. In region (1), the crossflow remains entirely outside the separation bubble. In region (2), however, the crossflow gradually intrudes into the separation bubble. By $z/H = 0.14$, the crossflow fully enters the separation bubble, accompanied by a sharp decrease in both its velocity and width.

FIGURE 7: (a) $U_x = 0$ ISO-SURFACE (RED) AND $U_z = 50$ m/s ISO-SURFACE (BLUE). (b) THE DISTRIBUTION POSITIONS OF MAXIMUM U_z AT DIFFERENT SPANWISE POSITIONS

At the boundaries between different regions, notable changes occur in the shape parameters of the separation bubble (see Figure. 8). When the short separation bubble (Region (1)) transitions into the medium separation bubble (Region (2)), the maximum thickness of the bubble ($y_{U_x=0,max}$) increases abruptly. At this location, the position of the peak spanwise velocity ($x_{U_z,max}$) of the crossflow is farthest downstream, and its magnitude reaches a maximum. This indicates that as the crossflow enters the separation bubble, it begins to mix with the separated shear layer, leading to a weakening of the crossflow and a significant increase in the thickness of the separation bubble. At the boundary between the medium separation bubble (Region (2)) and the long separation bubble (Region (3)), the axial location of the $y_{U_x=0,max}$ ($x_{U_z,max}$) shifts farthest downstream. Here, the crossflow has fully penetrated into the separation bubble. Near the boundary separating the long separation bubble (Region (3)) and the secondary separation

bubble (Region (4)), the $x_{y_{U_x=0,max}}$ abruptly moves downstream. Simultaneously, the axial flow direction of the crossflow gradually realigns, shifting from reverse flow to forward flow, which promotes the reattachment of the separated shear layer.

FIGURE 8: THE DISTRIBUTION POSITIONS OF MAXIMUM THICKNESS OF THE SEPARATION BUBBLE, SPANWISE MEAN VELOCITY AT DIFFERENT SPANWISE POSITIONS

These phenomena indicate that the structure of the suction-side separation bubble under end-wall effects exhibits a direct correlation with the crossflow originating from the end-wall. Therefore, elucidating how the separated shear layer transitions and reattaches under the influence of this crossflow is essential to uncover the underlying mechanisms responsible for the observed incoherence of the separation bubble.

3.2 Dynamics characteristics of the separated shear layer under crossflow effects

The separation-induced transition mechanism typically involves the formation of large-scale shedding vortices in the separated shear layer due to K-H instability, followed by vortex merging and breakdown, which ultimately induces transition^[19]. However, this mechanism was derived from studies on two-dimensional cascades without end-wall effects. The presence of crossflow is bound to alter the evolution of the separated shear layer. This section investigates how crossflow effects influence the dynamic characteristics of the separated shear layer.

As shown in Figure. 9, the iso-surface based on the Q-criterion ($Q = 2 \times 10^9$) reveals that the K-H shedding vortices lose their spanwise coherence under the influence of crossflow. It is evident that the distortion direction of the K-H vortices aligns with the variation in the position of $U_{z,max}$. Small-scale spanwise vortices (SV) still form in the corner region near the suction surface. These do not develop into large-scale shedding vortices

during their evolution. Additionally, distinct crossflow-induced vortices (CFIV) are observed around $z/H = 0.04\text{--}0.15$ (their generation mechanism will be explained in next section). Their streamwise size is significantly larger than that of the SV, indicating a fundamental change in the dynamic characteristics of the separated shear layer in this region.

FIGURE 9: DIFFERENT VORTICES REVEALED BY AN ISO-SURFACE BASED ON THE Q-CRITERION

By observing the transient vortex evolution process in Figure. 10(a), it is evident that all three types of vortices exhibit distinct periodic evolution characteristics. Therefore, monitoring points are inserted into the separated shear layer at the transition

location, and the transient pressure field was captured. After calculating the Power Spectrum Density (PSD), the dominant frequencies at the transition point across different spanwise positions are obtained, as shown in Figure. 10(b). At $z/H = 0.06$ and 0.12 , three high-intensity frequencies are observed: the characteristic frequency of the CFIV, with the former being the dominant frequency at this height ($f_d = 27,797$ Hz). Additionally, the characteristic frequency of the SV ($f_{sv} = 44,463$ Hz), generated by K-H instability, and its harmonic (f_h), are also detected, though its intensity is significantly lower than that of the CFIV frequency. Beyond $z/H > 0.12$, the dominant frequency is generated by K-H shedding vortices.

As illustrated in Figure. 10(c), within the range of $z/H < 0.14$, the fluctuation of the separated shear layer is predominantly governed by the characteristic frequency of the CFIV. The corresponding Strouhal number ($St_{\theta_s} = f_d \theta_s / U_s$) calculated by the boundary velocity (U_s) and momentum thickness (θ_s) at separation position is less than 0.005, which falls outside the range of K-H instability reported in previous studies ($0.005 < St_{\theta_s} < 0.008$) [20]. This further confirms that the transition and reattachment behavior of the separated shear layer within the $z/H < 0.14$ region is altered under the influence of the CFIV.

FIGURE 10: (a) DIFFERENT VORTICES EVOLUTION PROCESS. (b) THE PSD DISTRIBUTION OF TRANSIENT STATIC PRESSURE AT TRANSITION POSITIONS. (c) THE STROUHAL NUMBER AT SEPARATION POINT AT DIFFERENT SPANWISE POSITIONS.

The CFIV is generated through the interaction between the high-speed spanwise jet created by the impingement of the passage vortex (PV) on the suction surface, and the separated shear layer. As illustrated in Figure. 11(a), the generation of this crossflow jet shares the same frequency as the PV. When the crossflow jet passes through the height of $z/H = 0.06$, the separated shear layer is obstructed by it.

A monitoring line is inserted at the position in Figure. 11(a) to obtain the velocity profile of the separated shear layer (see Figure. 12). At $t = t_l + 90\Delta t$, the spanwise velocity increases

FIGURE 11: THE VARIATIONS OF (a) u_z AT $x/C_{ax} = 0.51$ AND (b) u_x AT $z/H = 0.06$ OVER TIME

FIGURE 12: THE PROFILES OF (a) u_z AND (b) u_x ALONG THE SAMPLING LINE AT $x/C_{ax} = 0.51$ AND $Z/H = 0.06$

Further analysis using the Q-criterion reveals the complete evolution process of the CFIV, as shown in Figure. 13. The vortex within the separation bubble is convected downstream by the incoming flow. Blocked by the crossflow jet, this bubble vortex is lifted upward and interacts with the incoming flow, inducing the formation and subsequent shedding of a CFIV. The

abruptly near the suction surface, corresponding to the emergence of the crossflow jet. Simultaneously, the streamwise velocity profile exhibits an inward indentation due to the blocking effect of the jet, leading to an increase in momentum thickness and a continuous instability enhancement in separated shear layer. In Figure. 11(b), a distinct protrusion appears at the location marked by the black dashed box at this specific moment, which corresponds to the formation of the CFIV.

shed vortex moves away from the suction surface while growing in size, while the original bubble vortex returns to its starting point, initiating a new induction cycle. Unlike the dynamics observed in a two-dimensional cascade, this process involves only a single non-stationary recirculation vortex within the separation bubble [21]. This vortex oscillates at the frequency of the crossflow jet, driven by the incoming flow, and continuously generates CFIV. Furthermore, the SV remains very weak throughout the process and is mostly merged by the CFIV.

FIGURE 13: THE EVOLUTION OF CFIV BASED ON Q-CRITERION AND TRANSIENT STREAMLINES AT $Z/H=0.06$

Under the influence of the end-wall effect, the $U_{z,max}$ of crossflow reaches its maximum magnitude at $z/H = 0.1$. Subsequently, $U_{z,max}$ decreases with increasing height (see Figure. 7(b)). As a result, the dynamic characteristics of the separated shear layer vary accordingly at different spanwise positions, leading to a redistribution of the intensities of the CFIV and K-H shedding vortex. The intermittency factor (γ)

distribution, averaged in the wall-normal direction near the surface, was obtained using the method proposed by Wang [22]. By examining the slope of the γ variation in Figure. 14, it is observed that under the combined influence of the CFIV and the SV, the growth rate of instability in the separated shear layer first increases, then decreases, and subsequently increases again as the spanwise height increases. This indicates that the amplification and decay of the CFIV and the K-H shedding vortex collectively affect the transition speed.

FIGURE 14: THE COMPARISON OF THE GROWTH RATE OF THE NORMAL AVERAGE γ AT DIFFERENT SPANWISE POSITIONS

The emergence of the CFIV alters the separation-induced transition mechanism. However, as the spanwise height increases and the crossflow weakens, the K-H shedding vortex is expected to reclaim dominance in the transition process. The relative contributions of these two vortex structures to the transition and reattachment of the separated shear layer require further investigation.

3.3 Transition and reattachment mechanism of the separated shear layer under crossflow effects

Within the corner region, both the CFIV and the SV generated by K-H instability promote the transition and reattachment of the separated shear layer. To quantitatively analyze their respective contributions to this process, this section employs the multiscale Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (mPOD) method to investigate the underlying mechanism under the influence of end-wall effects.

3.3.1 mPOD method

Proposed by Mendez [23], the mPOD method integrates multiresolution analysis (MRA) with classical proper orthogonal decomposition (POD). This approach operates by imposing

spectral constraints on the conventional POD, thereby decomposing the correlation matrix K into contributions across different scales. The process yields correlation matrices corresponding to non-overlapping frequency bands. These computations are based on a dataset of 1200 snapshots containing a combination of the transient velocity components in the axial, pitchwise, and spanwise directions (u , v , w). see Equations. (7) and (8),

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} u_{11} & \cdots & u_{N1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ u_{1J} & \cdots & u_{NJ} \\ v_{11} & \cdots & v_{N1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ v_{1J} & \cdots & v_{NJ} \\ w_{11} & \cdots & w_{N1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ w_{1J} & \cdots & w_{NJ} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$K = D^T D \quad (8)$$

where N and J represent the number of nodes and snapshots, respectively. The two-dimensional discrete Fourier transform is then applied to the matrix K :

$$\hat{K} = \bar{\psi}_F K \bar{\psi}_F \quad (9)$$

where ψ_F is the temporal structure of the discrete Fourier transform. The matrix K is decomposed into M components as

$$K \approx \psi_F \left[\hat{K} \odot H_L \right] \psi_F + \sum_{m=1}^{m=M-2} \psi_F \left[\hat{K} \odot H_{Bm} \right] \psi_F + \psi_F \left[\hat{K} \odot H_H \right] \psi_F \quad (10)$$

where H_L , H_B and H_H are Hadamard products of the one-dimensional transfer function $H \odot H^T$ used to obtain the filtering in the corresponding frequency bands. The orthogonal modes of each component are calculated as

$$K \approx \psi_L \sum_L^2 \psi_L + \sum_{m=1}^{m=M-2} \psi_{Bm} \sum_{Bm}^2 \psi_{Bm} + \psi_H \sum_H^2 \psi_H \quad (11)$$

The eigenvalues matrix sorted in descending order is expressed as

$$\psi_M = [\psi_L, \psi_{B1}, \psi_{B2}, \dots, \psi_H] \quad (12)$$

The mPOD modes are calculated as

$$\phi_M \approx D \psi_M \quad (13)$$

3.3.2 TKE generation analysis via mPOD method

For clarity of presentation, the K-H shedding vortices present in the range of $z/H > 0.14$ and the SV formed by the separated shear layer within $z/H < 0.14$ are collectively referred to as K-H SV in this section. The CFIV mode is obtained by superimposing the modes whose dominant frequency at each respective blade height matches the dominant frequency of the CFIV. Similarly, the K-H SV mode is constructed by superimposing modes based on the dominant frequency of the K-H SV.

As shown in Figure. 15(a), at $z/H = 0.06$, significant velocity fluctuations are observed in the CFIV mode, both downstream of the maximum thickness of the separation bubble and near the suction surface. These fluctuations are associated with intermittent crossflow jet. In contrast, no significant velocity fluctuations are detected in the K-H SV mode at this height, indicating that the CFIV dominates the unsteady flow at $z/H = 0.06$. Conversely, at $z/H = 0.4$, the situation is reversed, with the

K-H SV mode replacing the CFIV as the dominant source of flow unsteadiness.

The mPOD method is applied to the velocity field (u, v, w) from section 3.3.1 to extract distinct flow structures characterized. The modal eigenvalues quantify each structure's contribution to the total TKE, thus enabling loss mechanism analysis. The orthogonality of the mPOD allows the Reynolds stress to be computed via Equation. (14) [24]:

$$\overline{u'_i u'_j} = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N (\psi_m^n)^2 \phi_m^i \phi_m^j = \sum_{m=1}^N \Sigma_m \phi_m^i \phi_m^j \quad (14)$$

Thus, $\Sigma_m \phi_m^i \phi_m^j$ represents the total Reynolds stress of the m^{th} mPOD mode. Then, the production term of TKE (P_{TKE}) can be calculated as

$$P_{\text{TKE}} = -\rho \overline{u'_i u'_j} \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = \sum_{m=1}^N \left(-\rho \Sigma_m \phi_m^i \phi_m^j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} \right) \quad (15)$$

where $-\rho \Sigma_m \phi_m^i \phi_m^j \partial \bar{u}_i / \partial x_j$ expresses P_{TKE} of m^{th} mode. As shown in Figure. 15(b), which displays the P_{TKE} distribution for both the CFIV mode and the K-H SV mode, the P_{TKE} is concentrated in regions with strong velocity fluctuations, specifically downstream of the location of maximum separation bubble thickness. This indicates a direct correlation between the P_{TKE} and the intensities of both the CFIV and K-H SV.

FIGURE 15: THE (a) u_x AND (b) P_{TKE} DISTRIBUTION OF CFIV AND K-H SV MODES AT DIFFERENT SPANWISE POSITIONS

The next step involves analyzing how the contributions of velocity fluctuations generated by the CFIV and the K-H SV to the transition of the separated shear layer vary at different spanwise heights. Secondary instability is key to the transition from laminar to turbulent flow, determining its location and rate [3], and manifests as the generation of three-dimensional oblique waves [25]. This study uses the three-dimensional fluctuation

velocity, u'_{3D} (defined as $u'_{3D} = u' - u'_x$), to represent these oblique waves. As shown in Figure. 16, at $z/H=0.06$, the oblique waves generated at the boundary layer separation point propagate downstream until the reattachment location. In contrast, at $z/H=0.4$, the oblique waves propagate upstream from the transition point back towards the separation location. This phenomenon confirms the finding in section 4 that, under crossflow-induced transition, the recirculation vortex inside the separation bubble is not stationary but moves downstream, causing the oblique waves to propagate downstream with it. This behavior differs from the K-H instability-dominated transition, where a stationary recirculation vortex exists inside the upstream separation bubble [21]. Consequently, under crossflow-induced transition, the instability of the separated shear layer is primarily generated directly by its own inherent fluctuations, with no direct contribution from the downstream crossflow (the crossflow location is shown in Figure. 17). In contrast, the instability in a K-H-dominated transition stems mainly from the inherent K-H instability itself and the upstream propagation of perturbations from the K-H shedding vortices.

FIGURE 16: THE DISTRIBUTION OF u'_{3D} AT DIFFERENT SPANWISE POSITIONS

FIGURE 17: THE DISTRIBUTION OF U_z AT $z/H=0.06$

To further quantify the contributions of the CFIV and K-H SV to the transition of the separated shear layer, the perturbative P_{TKE} integrated between the separation and reattachment points for both the CFIV mode and the K-H SV mode is compared.

As shown in Figure. 18(a), the P_{TKE} of the CFIV mode initially increases and then decreases with increasing z/H , reaching a maximum at $z/H=0.12$. This trend aligns with the distribution of the maximum spanwise velocity in Figure. 7, where both the width and velocity of the crossflow are greatest in Region (2). This correlation demonstrates that stronger crossflow clusters lead to higher P_{TKE} in the CFIV mode.

In contrast, the P_{TKE} of the K-H SV mode increases to a maximum at $z/H=0.16$, then decreases, followed by a sudden increase at $z/H=0.36$ before continuing to decline. This behavior matches the variation in the maximum thickness of the separation bubble shown in Figure. 8, indicating that the thickness of the separation bubble determines the P_{TKE} of the K-H SV. The maximum bubble thickness at this location is attributed to the crossflow having just fully entered the separation bubble, where the crossflow intensity remains relatively high.

In terms of the total P_{TKE} , as illustrated in Figure. 18(b), the CFIV mode dominates the P_{TKE} of the separated shear layer in the range of $z/H < 0.14$, while the K-H SV mode dominates in the range of $z/H > 0.14$. The critical dividing point corresponds to the location where the crossflow fully enters the separation bubble, as indicated in Figure. 7(a).

FIGURE 18: THE COMPARISON OF (a) P_{TKE} AND (b) THE CONTRIBUTION RATIOS OF THE TOTAL P_{TKE} AT DIFFERENT SPANWISE POSITIONS

3.3.3 Crossflow-induced transition

Based on the research above, a new transition mode for the separated shear layer, termed crossflow-induced transition, has been identified. A schematic diagram is presented in Figure. 19. The PV periodically impinges on the corner region, inducing the formation of a crossflow jet with significant spanwise velocity. This process periodically generates CFIVs that move downstream within the corner region's separated shear layer. These CFIVs dominate the transition process in the corner region. Concurrently, weaker K-H SV generated by K-H instability are engulfed by the CFIV during their downstream movement.

FIGURE 19: SCHEMATIC OF THE CROSS-FLOW-INDUCED TRANSITION IN THE COMPRESSOR CASCADE CORNER

The presence of the crossflow alters the transition mode of the separated shear layer at different spanwise heights. The corner region, demarcated by the location where the crossflow fully enters the separation bubble, exhibits a crossflow-induced transition of the separated shear layer, while the other regions exhibit a transition induced by K-H instability.

4. CONCLUSION

Under low- Re conditions, high-intensity crossflow exists in the corner region of a compressor cascade, significantly altering the original transition pattern of the suction-side separated shear layer and resulting in an ambiguous transition mechanism. In this study, LES are performed on a subsonic compressor cascade, combined with the mPOD method, to investigate the dominant transition mode of the corner separated shear layer at $Re = 2.5 \times 10^5$ and to elucidate the underlying transition mechanism. The main findings are as follows:

- (1) The crossflow substantially influences the spanwise coherence of the suction-side separated shear layer. Under its effect, the separation bubble exhibits four distinct patterns from the blade root to the mid-span: short separation bubble, medium separation bubble, long separation bubble, and secondary separation bubble. The crossflow moves from the blade root toward the mid-span, initially appearing downstream of the short separation bubble. It then gradually reverses axial flow direction and flow into the medium separation bubble via crossflow separation, eventually fully enters the long separation bubble, and reverses its axial flow direction again to form the secondary separation bubble.
- (2) The CFIV alters the transition mechanism in the corner separated shear layer. Near the endwall ($z/H < 0.14$), the CFIV becomes the dominant flow structure. Its $St_{\theta s}$ lies below the classical K-H instability range, indicating a fundamental shift in

the transition mechanism. This vortex is generated by the interaction between the separated shear layer and the transverse jet along the suction surface and exhibits distinct periodicity. It engulfs the traditional K-H spanwise vortex and accelerates the transition process by driving the vortex within the separation bubble downstream, promoting the downstream propagation of three-dimensional oblique waves, which is proposed as a new transition process, ‘crossflow-induced transition’.

(3) The contributions of the crossflow and the K-H SV to the transition of the separated shear layer vary with spanwise height. Analysis based on mPOD decomposition and the P_{TKE} reveals that the CFIV dominates the P_{TKE} at $z/H < 0.14$, with its contribution peaking at the location of maximum crossflow velocity. In contrast, the K-H SV dominates at $z/H > 0.14$, where its P_{TKE} strongly correlates with changes in the separation bubble thickness—a variation itself governed by the crossflow intensity. The location where the crossflow fully enters the separation bubble ($z/H \approx 0.14$) serves as the critical boundary for the shift in dominance between the two transition mechanisms. And the spatial competition between the crossflow and the classical K-H instability is clarified.

In summary, this work elucidates the mechanism by which crossflow influences the separated shear layer, demonstrating that the crossflow-induced transition is the dominant transition process in the corner region. This finding holds significant implications for guiding the development of transition types. Furthermore, for controlling profile losses at low Re , it is essential not only to suppress separation in the suction-side boundary layer but also to curtail the development of the crossflow. This provides a new perspective for enhancing flow performance under low- Re conditions.

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